

**WONDERFUL CULTURAL HABITS OF DIFFERENT COUNTRIES
IN THE WORLD**

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Annotation: This article devoted to open the important features of culture, its function in human life. On the other hand, interesting facts about unusual cultural habits of different nation were given.

Key words: *customs, cultural heritage, cultural norm, expectations, beliefs, “mixed cultures”, religious beliefs, Culture traditions.*

Every country has its own special ways of doing things that show their history and make them stand out. Some people who are in a new country may think that everyone there should act and behave like they do. Cultural traditions show where someone came from, just like language. Culture is something that a person is brought up with and it becomes a part of them. These are things that you learn and believe in since you were born. People from different countries should understand that their behavior, expressions, gestures, and cultural practices may not be understood or appreciated the same way in other countries. All over the planet, there are many different ways of life. People have kept their tradition for a long time and passed it on to their kids. Cultures bring people together who have the same background, and help create communities. People from the same culture

usually think and believe similar things because they share the same cultural heritage. Culture is everything that makes up a group of people, like how they act and what they believe in. This can include things like art, laws, and habits. [1].

The traditions of a group of people are kept and passed down to their children and grandchildren. Culture traditions stay alive throughout history. Information, customs, ways of writing language, expectations for clothing, and so on. Some cultural things that are only found in one area's culture are called unique cultural traits. Culture is important to us because it tells us who we are and where we come from. Culture teaches us about the important beliefs and customs of our ancestors, which helps us understand the purpose of life. It helps us stand out compared to other places in the world. When we are born in a place, we learn the behaviors and beliefs of that place as we grow up. Our society also helps shape who we become. The customs and practices of our community can keep us connected for a long time. Keeping cultural heritage is important because it gives people a feeling of being part of something bigger and brings people together. Our ancestor's beliefs and customs are important and should be preserved so that we feel connected to them. A cultural norm is like a rule that tells us how to behave in society. It guides us on how to act, dress, talk, and behave in different situations. It is like a pattern that we follow to know what is expected of us in a social group. If a group of people only have one type of person, it can be risky. It's like if there was only one kind of plant and it couldn't adapt to changes, it would die out. [2]. The beliefs and laws laid down by the roots of our culture are meaningful and are for the betterment of our lives. Everything from marriage traditions to religious beliefs should be valued, in any culture. Even though times are changing now and “mixed cultures” are in fashion, effort to not let go of regional cultures are constantly carried out. As we know, every nation has its own culture and interesting customs that are different from other cultures. Below, we will consider several customs that do not repeat each other.

Choose the flowers you give to a Russian- if you have Russian business associates or friends, be careful of the flowers you give them. Avoid flowers with yellow colors as they represent a break-up of a relationship or deceit. Red carnations are taboo as well because these are flowers presented to veterans who survived the war and on the graves of those who have left this earth.

Be careful of what you give to Chinese colleagues- while China has opened its doors to the West, the cultural traditions of the Chinese will never be erased. They are one of the oldest civilizations in the world, so you have to understand that their cultural traditions were developed for millennia and handed down from generation to generation. The majority of the Chinese are superstitious as well and attach meanings to various things. When presenting your Chinese friends with flowers, avoid using white, which they associate with ghosts and death. In the United States, white flowers symbolize innocence and purity. Likewise, avoid flowers with thorny stems. Other things that are not good gifts for the Chinese are:

- *Clock*- Its name in Chinese (sòng zhōng, meaning send clock) sounds like sòng zhōng or funeral rite. It is also taken to mean that time is running out, or life and relationship can end.
- *Handkerchief* –In Chinese, it sounds like a farewell greeting.
- *Umbrella*- Offering or giving your Chinese friend or colleague an umbrella is a subtle hint of ending a relationship. You can share your umbrella but you have to take it back with you.
- Gifts that come in sets of *four*. The number 4 is associated with death.
- *Green hat*- Green is considered lucky by other people because it is the color of money. For the Chinese however, a green hat means that the wife is being unfaithful.

Don't ask for salt when dining in Egypt- in many cultures, like the United States, it is all right to ask for salt to add to your food. But if you are dining with friends and colleagues in Egypt, keep in mind to avoid asking for salt. It is taken as an insult to the host, as Egyptians take it to mean that you are repulsed by the taste of the meal served to you.

Mind your table manners in Norway- in some cultures, it is acceptable to eat food with your bare hands. But as etiquette would have it, it is often required that you use utensils such as a spoon and fork, chopsticks, or spoon, knife and fork when having a meal. Be sure to brush up on how to eat with a knife and fork before you travel to Norway. In this Scandinavian country, even sandwiches are eaten using a fork and a knife.

“No” to sharp objects- the cultural traditions of the Netherlands and China are vastly different. But in one thing, they are very similar and that is in the receiving gifts that are pointed and sharp, such as scissors and kitchen knives. Do not forget this – giving pointed and sharp objects to your friends or colleagues in the Netherlands (and in China) is a big no-no. For the Dutch, sharp objects are considered unlucky gifts, while for the Chinese, it means you want to break or cut ties with them.

In summary, we should keep our culture as our traditional way of life. No one should hurt or ruin our traditions. Our way of life and traditions shape who we are and it's important to remember that. We should keep passing it down to our children and their children, just like we have been doing. We should always remember our cultural background and make sure it doesn't disappear. A world where everyone has the same culture will be less interesting. The way people are brought up and taught by their families, schools, and communities can affect how they act as customers. This is called a company's cultural environment. Culture strongly influences what people buy and how they behave as consumers. It's

simple to say that culture is important, but harder to agree on what it really means. So, it's difficult to say exactly how culture affects what people buy. Different cultures between countries are different even more than the way they earn money, so it's hard to find common things among them.

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